

Analyzing Usability of Screen and Paper on Reading: An Eye Tracking Study

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Abstract

This study aims to examine whether misspelled types of text affect eye behavior while reading from paper and tablet screens. In addition, this study tests that participants tend to look at which sides of the print and screen while reading. The stimulus material that is used does not include any number, statistic symbol, or calculations. That is why Tobii X2-60 eye tracker device is used to record gaze movements. Tobii Studio Software 3.4.8 version is used to analyze gaze data and show findings in gaze plots and heat maps. The data were collected in laboratory settings. Participants were not informed about errors in stimulus material. The study aims to observe participants' gaze reflex and behavior whether realizing a misspelled word. In the experiment, participants read from paper and tablet respectively, which is Experiment.1 of this study.

Keywords: Eye movement, Reading behavior, Misspelled words

1. Introduction

Reading is a fundamental competence that is a learning process for all individuals. Screen and paper are reading media that are utilized mostly. The number of digital resources and collections increased over the last two decades [8]. However, people describe reading on a screen as less satisfying than on paper [5]. Reading speed on screen is 20% and 30% slower than on print [1]. This study was researched in 1988, people use mostly screens and computers over the last thirty years ago. However, there are eleven factors causing the difference comfortability between screen and paper: Orientation, eye movements, visual angle, aspect ratio, dynamics, flickers, image polarity, display characteristics, anti-aliasing, user characteristics, and the interaction of display variables [1]. Therefore, these factors might affect preferences in the reading process. However, people can still have difficulty and distractive factors while reading on screen in the last two decades. Therefore, individuals tend to skim, and scan on screen, which leads to not comprehending adequately on screen [4]. Digital environments are in daily uses for most people, which may cause a preference to read from screens.

People from the old generations tend to read on paper deeply because the quality of images was not efficient as nowadays (Dillon et. al., 1988). Although people use laptops, tablets, and mobile phones more than paper in a daily routine, they usually prefer reading from print-out reading. It is stated that despite the improved image quality and screen resolution attempts to produce convenient screens for human factors, screens are not practical compared to paper [2]. Despite the tendency in reading preferences toward paper, some changes in speed, accuracy, and comprehension due to use of digital devices in daily life, which is the aim of this study to analyze eye behaviors while reading.

Eye-tracking technology offers to detect eye movement directions, plots, and duration. Eye tracker devices enable investigation gaze focus points and dwell times that are time on a certain area [6]. Therefore, eye-tracking devices are used to analyze reading from paper and screen. Comparing these media to analyze usability and the human-computer interaction approach was conducted. Spelling errors create an area that distracts users' attention. Eye-gaze-based selection devices offer to identify the possible display with gaze plots, heat maps, and dwell time. Dwell time in eye tracking

Table 1. Participants' Distribution Regarding to Gender, Technic/Social Science, and Educational Levels

Participants' Distribution technic/social science, and educational levels (Comparing gender)	Technic/social sciences and educational level percentages				
	<i>Students studying a technic science</i>	<i>Students studying a social science</i>	<i>Students studying a Bachelor's Degree</i>	<i>Students studying a Master's Degree</i>	<i>Students studying a Ph.D. Degree</i>
female	55.56%	44.46%	55.56%	14.29%	33.33%
male	57.14%	42.86%	28.57%	28.57%	42.86%

technology is to examine fixations and saccades on a determined visual. Eye tracker devices and software enable comparative data to analyze and examine visual acuity according to participants' characteristics and determined areas in tests. Researchers compare gaze behavior to different types of misspelled words for participants. The researchers ask the following questions:

- How do participants' reading behavior change in terms of fixation counts and duration on mediums?
- Do participants' eye behavior change according to types of errors in the text?
- How do paper and screen media impact while realizing misspelled words?

2. Method

1. Participants. 16 university students (9 females, 7 males) from Middle East Technical University participated in the study voluntarily. Participants' age range is between 19 and 33 years old ($M: 26.38$, $SD: 3.86$). They were awarded a METU mug for their involvement. All participants were native Turkish, and the stimulus material was in Turkish. The researchers takes out in-

consistent data from statistics given from Tobii Studio 3.4.8 Software because a participant's hard contact lenses and a participant's calibration issue cause data loss.

2. Stimulus Material. The text used in the study was taken from How Serif and Sans Serif Typefaces Influence Reading on Screen: An Eye-Tracking Study [2]. The text consisted of 262 words that four of which are misspelling words. Errors in the text were orthographic errors such as missing letters, incorrect letters, replaced letters, and duplicate letters, which contained four misspelled words for four different types. Four misspelling words were balanced in the text. Stimulus material did not include any numbers, statistic percentages, or symbols because only words are analyzed for the study. In the material, characters were dark on a light background, which means positive polarity is tested. Positive polarity leads to better performance on small details because luminance causes small pupil size and sharper retinal images [7].

3. Procedure. A case study was used to investigate eye movements and duration on the general text and four different versions of an error on letters that are

Table 2. Fixation Count, Total Visit Duration (ms), and Fixation Duration on Paper versus Tablet Screen for All Participants

Fixation Count, Total Visit Duration (ms), and Fixation Duration on Paper Versus Tablet Screen	Average and Standard Deviation of Fixation Count, Total Recording Duration (ms), and Fixation Duration					
	<i>Fixation count</i>		<i>Total recording duration (ms)</i>		<i>Fixation Duration (ms)</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Paper	296.38	109.53	128,285.00	10,774.66	64,829.50	35,502.65
Tablet screen (iPad)	263.38	97.90	119,575.94	11,674.90	59,401.69	32,208.98

Table 3. Fixation and Regression Count of the Misspelled Words AOI on Paper versus Tablet Screen

Fixation and Regression Count of the Misspelled Words on Paper Versus Tablet Screen	Average and Standart Deviation of Fixation and Regression Counts of Misspelled Words (Comparing Media)							
	<i>Paper</i>				Tablet screen (iPad)			
	<i>Fixation count</i>		<i>Regression count</i>		<i>Fixation count</i>		<i>Regression count</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Letter omission	5.44	3.97	1.78	1.56	4.00	1.73	1.17	0.75
Letter substitution	9.45	4.52	2.91	1.45	6.00	2.97	1.91	1.51
Letter transposition	6.58	2.19	1.83	0.83	6.86	3.72	2.14	1.03
Letter addition	5.46	2.63	1.54	1.05	5.21	3.24	1.29	1.20

missing letters, incorrect letters, replaced letters, and duplicate letters on screen versus paper. Before the experiment begins, a tablet is a medium that has a light source beyond the text, the medium's light settings are auto-set to arrange according to METU Human-Computer Interaction laboratory room lighting level and luminance settings. HCI Laboratory is a dark room without any light sources other than four lumen lamps that were placed corners ceiling. participants complete a demographic survey and eye-tracking calibration. Sans Serif, 1.5 space between lines, and 11 font-size are used on both each medium (paper and tablet(iPad)). Participants were informed that gaze behavior and pupil size difference are recorded. The researchers ask that avoid moving the head and body and keep positions similar to the calibration position while reading. The researchers do not inform about letter errors on the document given to read. The researchers ask to read on paper and tablet devices loudly. Most participants ask "How do I read on misspelled words? Do I read mistakenly or not?". The researchers answer "You can read how you do prefer.". While reading, Tobii Eye Tracker X2-60 device and Tobii Studio 3.4.8 software version and recorded eye movements data that are fixations, saccade, duration, and gaze plots. The experiment lasted approximately 15 minutes in the laboratory setting. There was no time limit during the experiment. After participants finish reading, they were asked whether they remember misspelled words on the document. Participants were awarded a METU mug.

4. Limitations. In this study, all participants read on paper and tablet devices respectively because this test

is Experiment 1 which examines participants' features such as gender, educational level, social/technic science, and reading habit hours on print and digital screens in a week. This experiment is divided into Exp. 1 and Exp. 2 because the total number of participants must be about 20. The researchers separate participants into 4 groups that are social-female, technic-female, social-male, and social-female to examine eye tracking data.

3. Results and Findings

The demographics for experiment, 16 participants (9 females, 7 males) are between 19 and 33 years old (M: 26.38 SD: 3.86). 75% of all participants (66.67% females, 85.71% males) read for 3-6 hours on a print-out in a week. 75% of all participants (66.67% females, 85.71% males) read for more than 20 hours on a screen in a week. According to [3], interest in an area increases with the increase in fixation count proportionally. Participants read with more fixation count and duration on paper than on screen. However, all participants read on paper and the tablet screen (iPad) respectively. Participants read the same stimulus material two times. That is why participants can read faster on the tablet. In addition, fixation count and duration might decrease because of reading two times the same material. The average fixation count on paper decreases while reading on the screen by 11.13% (decreasing by SD: 8.94%). The average fixation duration on paper decreases while on the tablet screen by 8.37% (decreasing by SD: 9.28%). Despite the average count fixation count decreasing by 11.13% while reading on the tablet screen, the average fixation duration decreases by

Table 4. Total Duration of Fixations and Regressions on Misspelled Words AOI on Paper versus Tablet Screen

Total Duration of Fixations and Regressions on Misspelled Words on Paper Versus Tablet Screen	Total Duration of Fixation and Regression (Comparing Media)							
	Paper				Tablet screen (iPad)			
	Total duration of fixations (ms)		Total duration of regressions (ms)		Total duration of fixations (ms)		Total duration of regressions (ms)	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Letter omission	1251.1	865.1	466.4	505.8	906.2	269.2	222.3	143.0
Letter substitution	2409.8	1342.4	712.2	438.5	1568.6	1118.7	608.8	592.2
Letter transportation	1599.4	895.9	487.7	342.7	1619.7	673.6	555.4	299.8
Letter addition	1286.9	794.7	390.0	324.9	1388.9	944.3	312.5	326.3

8.37%. Therefore, participants read with less the average fixation number count and shorter fixation duration on the tablet screen versus on paper.

Letter errors can cause a distraction while reading. Therefore, participants can be interested in misspelled words, which affect fixation count and duration. Distracted words might increase attention in stimulus material, which means that number of fixation and regression on gaze data increases. Furthermore, we collected data for determining more distractive faults on words. According to Table 3, letter substitution distracts more than other errors on paper while letter transposition cause to loss of concentration on the tablet. In addition, regression (turning back while reading) count indicates that letter substitution on paper and letter transposition on the tablet screen are more distractive than other error types.

According to Table 4, letter substitution on paper causes longer fixation and regression duration time. On the tablet screen, the average fixation duration on letter transposition is longer than others. Even though the regression duration of letter transposition is shorter than letter substitution, the standard deviation of substitution is more than others. Therefore, letter substitution and transposition distract respectively on paper and the tablet screen.

Table 5 offers information where participants look at the paper and the tablet. Tobii Studio 3.4.8 recording resolution is 640*360 px. Findings show that participants look at the middle on paper and the screen. Therefore, results infer that participants have average fixations on the center for both print-out and tablet. The standard deviation difference between the media is a few. Hence, Table V indicates that the average and

Table 5. Average Gaze Point (Fixation) X and Y Axis on Paper versus Screen

Average Fixation Point X and Y (px) on paper versus screen	Average and Standard Deviation of Fixation Point X and Y (px)			
	Fixation Point X (MCSPx)		Fixation Point Y (MCSPx)	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Paper	326.3	60.6	194.9	41.6
Tablet screen (iPad)	326.1	60.5	194.4	41.6

standard deviation of fixation points do not show a significant difference comparing paper and tablet screens.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In Experiment.1, participants who are studying at METU contribute voluntarily. Participants read the same stimulus on paper and the tablet device respectively. Hence, the expectation of Experiment.1 is that participants can read in a shorter time on the tablet. Findings indicate that fixation number and duration are less on screen than on paper. The difference between them is less than 10%, which can be neglectable because of reading the same stimulus twice. Therefore, the researchers can say that the expectation happens and there is no significant difference between reading paper versus tablet screen. In addition, the middle of the paper and screen is convenient. Letter substitution on paper and letter transportation on the tablet screen take attention significantly.

5. Acknowledgment

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